

1 **USE OF DEEP LEARNING FOR AUTOMATIC DETECTION OF CRACKS IN**
2 **TUNNELS – PROTOTYPE-2 DEVELOPED IN THE 2017-2018 TIME PERIOD**

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1 **ABSTRACT**

2 Cracks on the surfaces inside road tunnels are among the most critical problems in the management
3 of such tunnels and, if not properly addressed, can have severe consequences in terms of safety
4 and costs. Nowadays, the main techniques used for analysis of such surfaces make use of either
5 human inspections or complex automated systems, which are respectively very time consuming
6 and expensive, and/or difficult to implement. There is therefore great interest in a low-cost data
7 acquisition platform coupled with Artificial Intelligence (AI) based automated crack detection
8 system. This paper introduces a low cost technique for road tunnel inspections based on a simple
9 system that does not require complex preliminary work and can be used also in tunnels with a
10 normal traffic flow. In particular, thanks to a second-generation data acquisition system developed
11 in the 2017-2018 academic year, a series of high-resolution pictures can be obtained and used in a
12 pre-trained deep neural network able to identify the presence of cracks through the classification
13 of the pictures. Thanks to deep learning techniques, it is possible to exploit the power of Inception-
14 v4, a deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) provided by Google which can be retrained for
15 the specific purpose of crack detection. This kind of network has been trained with a pictures
16 database generated using a second data acquisition prototype developed during the 2017-2018
17 academic year.

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22 *Keywords:* Deep Learning, Inception Network, Crack Detection, Tunnels, Automation,
23 Inspection, Concrete, Assessment

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1 INTRODUCTION

This paper is focused on road tunnels as key part of modern transportation infrastructure. The rapid urbanization of cities around the globe and the corresponding exponential growth in transportation infrastructure to support ever increasing population densities, has led to the corresponding increase in road tunnels as a means of alleviating congestion, where and when possible. This necessitates development of automated techniques for detection of cracks on the surfaces inside tunnels given the high costs of manual visual inspection both monetarily and in terms of time.

In addition, the growth of the sub-urban sprawl to provide affordable housing has accelerated the construction of tunnels, which became very useful for re-directing traffic flows and reducing congestions. Structural integrity testing of the road tunnels imposes the first problem of managing the traffic flow during the inspections, since it may not always be possible to block the traffic and examine the entire tunnel to perform a human visual inspection or to prepare and mount a complex robotic structure for the same purpose. Furthermore, the number of tunnels may be large, leading to potentially expensive inspection systems in terms of money and time that may not be affordable, especially in the developing countries. In this scenario, a low-cost automatic system can be a smart solution and can overcome many of the previously described problems.

The system described in this paper is based on deep learning, and in particular on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which in recent years have shown great potential in the image classification and object recognition fields. We recall that a huge step forward in this approach was the introduction of the transfer learning techniques, which allows one to use a pre-existing network to solve a broad range of problems, via training the decisional layer of the pre-trained deep CNN. This allows adapting a deep network and tailoring it to a specific purpose by retraining the decisional layers while keeping all of the other trained layers intact. Such layers have been extensively pre-trained to identify basic features in images. In this paper we wish to exploit the power of the 48 layer deep CNN *Inception-v4 network* proposed by Google, by adapting it to our core objective of classifying our pictures in two classes; those that show cracks and those that do not. Artificial Intelligence (AI) based techniques seem to perform much better for our application than classical image processing based approaches. Once the deep CNN is properly trained, it can classify images in a very short time. The implementation of such a system does not require complex infrastructure or equipment.

Training of Inception-v4 network employing transfer learning to detect tunnel cracks requires a sufficiently large database of images that are difficult to find in the open literature, thus necessitating the construction of a prototype data acquisition system. Development of the data acquisition system on the other hand poses its own challenges given the difficult environmental conditions of tunnels. Key concerns include hazards due to traffic operations, poor lighting, CO gas, dust, etc. This paper reports on the development of a second-generation low-cost data acquisition system for image acquisition from surfaces inside tunnels. At the time of this writing, the functionality of the prototype has been verified, but the collection of pictures is not sufficiently numerous to run transfer learning with highest confidence. Still, even in presence of a partial acquisition, the trained network can provide results with better than 90% accuracy, thanks to a proper setting of the hyperparameter of the deep CNN network.

2 RELATED WORKS

As noted earlier, an automatic system for detection of cracks on the surfaces inside a tunnel is a very challenging problem, ripe for R&D in terms of finding better solutions for data acquisition and automating the process by using deep neural networks. Different solutions have been proposed during the past few years, even if this field as a whole is still at its infancy.

The first proposed techniques in literature were based on image processing techniques, and not on deep learning algorithms, but can be considered very inspiring from the hardware point of view and for providing examples of different data acquisition systems. For example, in 2007 Hanyang University (1) built a robotic system able to detect images inside a tunnel and then process them in order to find cracks in the concrete. This mobile robot was remotely controlled in order to maintain constant distance from the tunnel walls and it was equipped with CCD cameras, in order to get images under the best possible conditions. The image capture system was also equipped with illuminators and encoders for computing speed and position of the robot in the tunnel. From the software point of view, the images were processed with computer vision techniques in order to find images with cracks and measure their characteristics. Even though the measurements of cracks were very good once detected, the system was very inefficient in crack detection, with an error rate of around 80 %. In another development, a Taiwanese team proposed a new method (*Image-mosaic technology*) for reconstructing 3D tunnel surfaces from images taken with cameras (2). While the aim of the R&D conducted by the Taiwanese team was different from ours, the common element was the necessity of having a good database of images.. In (3) the authors proposed the use of Digital Single Lens Reflex (DSLR) cameras for image acquisition; in particular, they built a circular array of five DSLR cameras arranged on a remotely controllable rail, in order to image all the internal surfaces of the tunnel. While the approach proposed is interesting and our prototype also utilizes a DSLR camera, our aim is to develop a simple system at much lower cost point that is portable and can be mounted on any vehicle. An interesting work was presented in 2013 (4), when researchers created an acquisition system on a truck moving in normal traffic flow inside a tunnel in order to develop a system that does not require a complete blockage of the tunnel segment under scrutiny.

One of the first application of CNNs to the problem of crack detection, was presented by a team in (5) which proposed a vision based method using deep neural architecture for classification of images with or without cracks. The proposed architecture however was not based on recent developments in deep networks and was composed of only 2-convolutional layers, with a last softmax layer for the final classification of the pictures. In that work, the authors took more than 100000 images and used 80 % of them for the training set. The objective of the project was to compare the Neural Network (NN) based approach with other computer vision based algorithms and, by looking at the results, the authors asserted that NN technique is widely better than many of the other image processing approaches.

One of the best result with these new techniques was achieved by Cha and Choi in 2017, (6). The images for the training of the network had been taken with a DSLR camera inside a tunnel in Manitoba and more than 40000 images had been collected. In particular, 80% of the acquired images were used as training set, while 10% each were used for testing and validation. The results obtained by running the algorithm on two GPUs were excellent, with around 97% accuracy in crack detection in the testing phase. Another work presented in the literature regarding the tunnel inspection is the ROBOSPECT European FP7 project (7), whose objective is that of building a complete autonomous robot able to collect images without human help and then process them using a convolutional network in order to identify the presence of a crack. The robot is very

1 complex itself; it is composed of a standard mobile vehicle with an extended crane with a robotic
2 arm. The computer vision system was composed of two CCD cameras and two DSLRs and a
3 powerful lighting system mounted on the robotic arm. The robot also has a 3D laser scanner with
4 the alleged ability to detect the depth of the crack. When the images are processed by the CNN
5 and a crack is detected, the robotic arm is moved close to the crack and the 3D laser is activated
6 for depth measurements.

7 While this project focused on one technology, other Non-Destructive Examination (NDE)
8 technologies, including but not limited to LiDAR, Impact-Echo (IE) analysis, Thermal/InfraRed
9 (IR) analysis, machine vision, might also have future promising research opportunities for concrete
10 crack detection.

11 **3 THE DEVELOPED SYSTEM**

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14 Our proposed system is composed of two main elements, the image acquisition system and the
15 deep neural network. The first one, as previously explained, aims at collecting images for the
16 analysis of the surfaces inside tunnels and generating a proper dataset for the training the network.
17 The second element is a software program, which runs on a separate hardware and is used to train
18 the Inception-v4 deep CNN for our purposes.

19 **3.1 Acquisition system**

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22 The idea behind this acquisition system is to devise a low-cost system that is, at the same time,
23 easily reusable and does not require a complex infrastructure. The main goal of this system is to
24 create a dataset for training the deep CNN. In order to obtain acceptable results in the training of
25 the network, a large number of high-resolution images must be acquired.

26 A very cheap video capture equipment operating in the infrared regime, from which (thanks to a
27 post-processing phase) a series of pictures have been extracted, characterized the first generation
28 prototype that was developed and tested in the 2016-2017 academic year. In the second-generation
29 prototype presented here, the acquisition procedure has completely changed, and it is based on
30 images acquired directly using a DSLR camera. We chose it thanks to the good results that this
31 kind of cameras produced in several works presented in the literature and referenced in the
32 previous sections. The other problem is clearly the tunnel inspection method, because the expected
33 result is a system that has to work inside urban tunnels without disturbing the traffic flow to the
34 extent possible. To accomplish this, the whole data acquisition system was envisaged to be a
35 portable platform that could be easily mounted on the roof of any vehicle using roof racks. Once
36 mounted, the electronic systems on the platform could be controlled from inside the vehicle, the
37 main requirement being supplying power to the unit. The designed and developed system is
38 composed of four main components: DSLR camera, lighting system, radio-frequency remote
39 control and camera control unit.

40 The chosen DSLR camera is the *CANON EOS800D* model, with a 55mm lens. This model satisfies
41 all the quality constraints required by our application. The 24MP picture resolution guarantees
42 extremely good pictures, which can be taken at relatively high speed (up to nominal 6 frames per
43 second or fps) and in different modes. Moreover, the manual mode of the camera allows the user
44 to set all the parameters of the camera manually, in order to adapt the camera to the difficult
45 environmental conditions of tunnels. Another important feature of the camera is the capability of
46 being controlled remotely through its PC cable by an external CPU, which is crucial for the system
47 in order to have a camera able to shoot without the human interference.

1 For this prototype we focused on the lighting system, which plays a very important role in this
2 kind of application. Inside a tunnel, we usually have poor lighting conditions and so the camera
3 must be assisted by external light source in order to produce clear pictures. Two light sources have
4 been selected, one fixed light source and a camera-flash. The fixed light source is a 500-LED Panel
5 (*Neewer 500LED Photo Studio Lighting Panel*), that is useful to create a strong and clear light.
6 Synchronously, we also used the *Neewer NW-561 LCD Display Speedlite Flash* to generate a
7 strong light source with the camera in order to improve the contrast on the pictures taken.

8 Moreover, we use radio frequency remote control in order to create a wireless connection between
9 the camera and the flash mentioned above. In addition, it is essential to improve the scalability of
10 the acquisition process; in a plausible expansion of the system with more cameras and flashes, they
11 can be synchronized through this kind of control. PocketWizards offer a reasonable solution in
12 terms of costs and quality. The company produces a variety of instruments for the flash and camera
13 synchronization. A pair of *PLUSIII* have been chosen in our system. One of them is connected to
14 the camera through its own hotshoe, while the other is connected to the flash through a provided
15 cable.

16 Finally, the camera control has to activate the shooting functions of the camera. For this purpose,
17 a *Raspberry PI3* has been selected, basically for the reduced dimensions which allow us to easily
18 place it on the mounting platform and to connect it to the camera through a PC cable. The
19 Raspberry is controlled through an external keyboard and a 7" LCD display. However, the main
20 reason behind the choice of a Raspberry PI, is the capability to exploit the power of the Python
21 library *gphoto2*. A simple Python code has been developed in order to activate the shutter release
22 of the camera at its maximum speed (it is like having the shutter constantly held down by a finger).
23 Thanks to this technique, the camera produces pictures at the maximum speed allowed and the
24 execution of the program can be easily stopped when needed.

25 The overall system is presented in (Figure 1) and (Figure 2), and adheres to all the constraints
26 previously explained, with a total cost of below \$2000. Everything is assembled on a homemade
27 platform, which is composed of a wooden base and an aluminum-based frame that allows the entire
28 platform to be tilted to take pictures from different angles, and steel camera holders.
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30 **3.2 Collected Dataset**

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32 Our prototype has been designed to be able to capture a large number of pictures without loss of
33 quality. To find the best parameter set, several tests have been performed in a dark room, so that
34 the environmental conditions can reproduce the ones present during the real experiment. First, we
35 consider the image-acquisition speed, which is set at the highest possible rate and represents a
36 fixed constraint for data acquisition at normal driving speed of about 30 Km/hr. Our tests have
37 shown that in order to extend the number of acquired images, it is better to set every parameter
38 mode manually. In this way, it is possible to avoid the auto-setting of the camera, which introduces
39 a small post-processing delay in the shooting time that is undesirable. Thanks to the powerful
40 camera, we are able to capture more than one photo per second, while maintaining a good image
41 resolution. Indeed, we were able to acquire at least 3 *images/second* driving at 30 *km/h*. This
42 way, we could guarantee a proper number of good photos in the tunnel covering all regions of
43 interest, without interfering with the traffic flow.

44 Three camera parameters have been modified: ISO speed (for controlling the light sensitivity of
45 the camera), the aperture (for the background blur) and shutter speed (for objects in motion). The
46 used setting is ISO3200, F4.5 aperture and 1/400 shutter speed. The focus of the lens has been left

1 to the automatic procedure of the camera. During several tests directly performed in the tunnels,
2 the automatic modes available on the camera did not respond well and not just in terms of speed
3 of the shutter. For example, in sport mode (which at first thought may appear to be suitable for the
4 application at hand) the camera produces pictures that are completely out of focus and cannot be
5 used.

6 As mentioned earlier, the data collection task is not completed as of this writing. So far, our dataset
7 is composed of 1024 pictures of which 521 show surfaces with potential cracks. An example of
8 one picture collected with the camera showing the extremely high resolution obtained is shown in
9 (Figure 3).

11 3.3 Inception-v4 and Transfer Learning

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13 Transfer learning is a machine learning technique able to use a neural network in a specific
14 application different from the one for which it has been pre-trained (8). A Convolutional Neural
15 Network (CNN) is often structured in such a way that the first layers aim to find basic and common
16 patterns (like edges, colors etc.) from a collection of training images, while the last layers
17 effectively perform the classification functions for which the network has been designed for. In
18 this way, through transfer learning, a user can use the learning power of a network until the last
19 layers and retrain only the decisional layers to his/her specific application. In this paper, we used
20 the Inception-v4 (9) network which is the latest version of Google-Net, a powerful deep neural
21 network presented by a Google team in the ImageNet Visual Recognition Challenge in 2012 (10).
22 Inception-v4 is a 48 layers deep network, based on the innovative concept of *Network in Network*
23 structure (11), which has been trained by Google with powerful GPUs. This kind of deep network
24 requires weeks for being well trained from scratch and requires a huge dataset to be sufficiently
25 generalized to be used for a multitude of applications. Once the core network is trained however,
26 thanks to transfer learning it is possible to retrain only the last layer of the network (i.e., the
27 decisional layer), which is a not a very time consuming operation for reasonably sized datasets.
28 Inception-v4 is a network which classifies images in certain classes provided by the user, so it is
29 perfectly usable for the crack detection problem at hand. During the retraining process, it is
30 possible to set different hyperparameters in order to adapt the network as much as possible to the
31 provided dataset, for example adjustments can be made to the learning rate or the dimension of the
32 different data batches.

34 3.2.1 Results and considerations

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36 (Table 1) shows the results obtained by the retraining process with several choices of
37 hyperparameters. The tests have been performed with the dataset previously described, divided
38 into a training set (80% of the images), validation set (10% of images), and test set (10% of images).
39 The results have been evaluated in terms of test accuracy (the percentage of correctly classified
40 images seen for the first time after the training) and cross entropy value on the last training sample,
41 since the cost function used for the learning procedure is the cross entropy between the expected
42 and obtained result. The network works with images with resolution of 299x299 pixels.

43 The software has been run on a *HPZ840 Workstation*, which uses an *Intel Xeon CPU* processor
44 at 2.2GHz and 16GB of RAM.

45 As stated previously, the current dataset is not large enough for this kind of application, nonetheless
46 the detection accuracies are encouraging. Moreover, applications involving image processing can
47 be executed much faster when run on a GPU, which has not been used in this first development

1 stage.

2 Note that a test accuracy of 97.8% has been achieved in Test #7, which is a very good result for
3 the current structure of the network and the current equipment; this means that the network
4 misclassified (i.e., did not detect a crack when there was one or detected a crack that was not
5 present) only 11 of the 512 tested images. Out of these 11 misclassifications, 9 were “false
6 positives” (i.e. a crack was detected where there was not one) and 2 were “false negatives” (i.e. the
7 presence of a crack was missed by the algorithm).

8 Some results are also affected by overfitting, which may occur in presence of a small dataset.
9 Overfitting is a bad condition during the training phase and it arises when the network starts to
10 remember the training images “by heart” and effectively stops to learn. A clear example is shown
11 in (Figure 4), which refers to Test #1, where it is possible to appreciate how after 2000 iterations
12 the training accuracy (orange line) remains constant and equal to 100%, which means that the
13 network learned only the specific aspects of the training images and not the general patterns of the
14 presence of a crack. In fact, the Test #1 validation accuracy is effectively far from 100%. The best
15 way to overcome the overfitting problem is to enlarge the dataset or to modify heuristically the
16 hyperparameters, but different tests we conducted has verified our belief that the big problem is
17 effectively the size of the dataset. One possible way to handle this problem can be the artificial
18 expansion of the data, obtained by rotating or cropping the images in order to increase the number
19 of available pictures. Unfortunately, the current equipment is too slow for artificial data expansion
20 and a simple retraining can take weeks, losing completely the good aspects of the transfer learning
21 technique.

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23 **4 CONCLUSIONS**

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25 In this paper we have described the design, development and testing of a low-cost prototype for
26 automatic crack detection on surfaces inside road tunnels. The first results produced are effectively
27 promising and we obtained a 94.5% test accuracy with a small dataset and without a GPU.
28 Moreover, our outcomes demonstrate how transfer learning could produce good results in tackling
29 the crack detection problem. Finally, this relatively low-cost prototype produces high-quality
30 images at normal driving speeds, provided the parameter set of the DSLR camera is properly
31 adjusted.

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33 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT**

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35 The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: F.
36 Daneshgaran, L. Zacheo, F. Di Stasio, M. Mondin; data collection: L. Zacheo, F. Di Stasio; analysis
37 and interpretation of results: F. Daneshgaran, L. Zacheo, M. Mondin; draft manuscript preparation:
38 F. Daneshgaran, L. Zacheo, M. Mondin. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final
39 version of the manuscript.

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FIGURE 1: The overall system composed of LED lighting system, DSLR camera, PLUSIII sync system and standalone flash, Raspberry PI, 7" LCD display for programming, and cables.

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FIGURE 2: The system mounted on the minivan.

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FIGURE 3: Example of a picture taken from the wall inside a tunnel obtained using the designed and developed prototype-2 system.

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FIGURE 4: Accuracies on Test #1. Horizontal axis is the neural network training iteration index, while the vertical axis is the classification accuracy on scale of 0 to 1, with 1 being 100%.

TABLE 1: Test Results.

Test Number	Iterations	Learning Factor	Train Batch Size	Validation Batch Size	Evaluation Interval	Cross Entropy	Test Accuracy
1	4500	0.1	100	202	100	0.002974	92.7%
2	2000	0.1	100	100	100	0.002808	93.6%
3	1000	0.1	100	100	100	0.009057	91.7%
4	2500	0.01	100	100	100	0.02428	93.6%
5	6000	0.001	100	100	100	0.07742	94.5%
6	9000	0.001	100	100	100	0.104863	93.6%
7	7000	0.01	200	100	100	0.007842	97.8%
8	2000	0.1	75	100	100	0.003804	92.7%
9	2000	0.1	150	100	100	0.006381	92.7%
10	9000	0.001	50	100	100	0.055273	93.6%

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